

WAYS OF OVERCOMING LANGUAGE BARRIER IN SPEAKING

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Abstract: Many learners struggle to speak confidently because of psychological barriers such as fear of making mistakes, shyness. This article discusses the main psychological factors that prevent students from speaking freely. It also presents modern techniques and artificial intelligence-based tools that can help us to reduce anxiety, improve fluency, and build confidence. By using communicative activities, peer collaboration, and AI-supported applications it is possible to gain better speaking skills in a more relaxed and supportive learning environment.

Keywords: speaking skills, psychological barriers, language anxiety, speaking confidence

Speaking is recognized as one of the difficult skills in the process of language learning. Despite years of studying, many learners have difficulty speaking freely due to psychological barriers, lack of vocabulary, and fear of making mistakes..With the rapid development of innovative teaching and artificial intelligence technologies, educators have useful tools to help students to overcome these obstacles. This article outlines causes of psychological barrier and a range of modern techniques and AI-driven applications and how they can reduce anxiety, build communicative competence, and help to develop fluent, confident speech.

To overcome the language barrier students must know what is blocking them from speaking confidently. Barriers are categorised into different groups including semantic, physical, organizational and psychological.

Psychological barriers are one of the most influential factors as many learners experience fear of making mistakes, general shyness. Firstly psychological barriers come from personal motives, social values and overthinking about process. These create psychological distance which means it causes misunderstanding among people and it makes communication less effective

Another cause is selective perception-based upon our needs, motives, experience, background we have our own limitations and different perception. As a result of different conclusions, assessments we can experience with misunderstandings and misinterpretations. It can be also called 'Different comprehension of reality'¹¹

There are several techniques to overcome psychological barrier

Micro-speaking activities: Students to speak for 30-90 seconds on simple topics independently or with partners. It can be also called JAM (just a minute) technique which reduce fear, help shy students start gradually and build confidence overtime. Advertising the things, places that they see on daily basis, describing current events or objects that use daily can be great examples¹²

Communicative tasks and real-life scenarios: Ordering food, giving directions, sharing opinion (information-gap) or solving practical problems in chosen foreign language the students focus on situation rather than achieving perfect accuracy. They feel less pressure and develop greater fluency and confidence

Peer coaching and collaborative speaking: In this technique we can work in pairs or small groups to support each other's speaking development using structured frameworks: sentence starters, guided questions or conversation cards. By implementing discipline such as 1 hour peer practice for a day only in learning language, they can learn to guide discussions, give opinions. By using this technique step by step students can achieve to lose the general shyness together.¹³

¹¹ (margheritacollege, 2024)

¹² Kathleen M. Bailey, 1994 'New ways in teaching speaking' Alexandria, USA; Library of Congress Catalogue part 1 page 3-117

¹³ C. Richards, 2006 'communicative language teaching today' Cambridge University Press

Artificial intelligence technology have revolutionized the way we practice speech. Tools such as Elsa Speak and Speechling provide real-time c. -AI chatbots like ChatGpt and Replika allow learners to have meaningful discussions, eliminate fear, and build confidence. In addition taboo talks platform is designes as word-guessed game which makes learning enjoyable .In the given article the author included prompts to make the process easier. AI can also suggest improved phrase patterns, extend vocabulary, and direct shadowing activities to improve fluency and intonation. With given feedback and progress tracking, students may focus on their weak areas and practice successfully.

However, it is critical to repeat it and make it a daily habit, as gaining confidence with only a few conversations or comments is difficult.¹⁴

In conclusion, fear of mistakes, overthinking, and shyness often reduce students' willingness to communicate. However, these difficulties can be overcome with the help of several techniques and artificial intelligence technologies

XORIJIY TILLARNI O‘QITISHDA INNOVATSION METODLAR VA AI TEXNOLOGIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada chet tillarini o‘qitishda innovatsion metodlar va sun’iy intellekt (AI) texnologiyalarining o‘rni hamda ulardan foydalanish

¹⁴ (Mondeera Pituxcoosuvam, May 2025)